

EMERGING DATA ARCHIVES: PROVIDING DATA SERVICES WITH LIMITED RESOURCES

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INTRODUCTION

- The establishment of data services is a long and challenging process
 - During the initial phase, a potential SP is able to gain necessary knowledge and experience, but after that it has to offer some services to users
 - Based on Croatian and Serbian experience we will analyze alternative modes for providing data services with limited resources and budgetary constraints
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A LITTLE BIT OF HISTORY

FIRST STEPS TOWARD DATA SERVICES IN CRO AND SER

- **Croatia**
 - 2006 - Initiative for establishment of national social sciences data archive in Croatia
 - 2007 - gaining experience in preparing data from pre-election studies to be archived at GESIS
 - 2009 - on the roadmap for CESSDA widening identified by CESSDA-PPP
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A LITTLE BIT OF HISTORY

FIRST STEPS TOWARD DATA SERVICES IN CRO AND SER

- **Serbia**

- February 2002 - GESIS and UNDP organized workshop „Social Science Data Archive in Eastern Europe – Results, Potentials and Prospects of the Archival Development“
 - Representative: Center for Political Studies and Public Opinion Research, University of Belgrade
 - NEDA (National Data Archive) without success due to numerous constrains
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FP 7 SERSCIDA PROJECT (2012-14)

JOINT EFFORT WITH CESSDA SUPPORT

- Start from scratches
 - Analysis of existing potentials for the establishment of a social sciences digital data archive in our countries (survey)
 - Raising awareness (round tables, conferences)
 - Prepare the establishment plan separate for each country
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ESTABLISHMENT PLAN

AS A STARTING POINT (BRIEFLY OVERVIEW)

1. Founders institutions
 2. Scope of collection: quantitative and qualitative data (sociology, psychology, education science, information science, political science, and economics)
 3. Establish the set of services to be provided
 - Declaratively we anticipate a wide range of services
 4. Financing scheme and budget - 2-5 year projects
 5. Governance structure (e.g. oversight board, scientific board)
 6. Human Resources, Technical infrastructure, Policies, quality control procedures, and workflows
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SCOPES SEEDS PROJECT (2015-17)

BUILDING DATA COLLECTIONS AND ENHANCING TOOLS

- FORS (Swiss) and ADP (Slovenia) support
- Using their resources (infrastructure and know-how) we will:
 - Build our collections (min 10 datasets) and
 - Extend the prototype technical system put into place by SERSCIDA

CESSDA SaW PROJECT (2015-17)

EXPLORING POLICY AREAS

- Data services will be benchmarked against the target level of an ideal mature CESSDA Service Provider
- Create individual national development plans and “media packs”, in collaboration with ministries/research councils and possible future CESSDA Service Providers

THE MAIN COMMON ISSUES WE ARE FACING WITH

- Development of data centers is only supported by the European community and international projects
 - Lack of support from relevant ministries
 - Heavily dependent on political situation
 - Huge budget constraints
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WHAT CAN WE DO AND WHICH SERVICES CAN WE PROVIDE?

- continue to work on ongoing projects (SEEDS and CESSDA SaW - perfect match)
 - look for more funding opportunities
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MAIN SERVICES

- Curation and long-term preservation of data
- Online catalogue of archived data
- Dissemination of data for use in secondary analysis

(classification of services taken from ongoing work within the H2020 CE3SDA SaW project)

ADDITIONAL SERVICES AND ACTIVITIES

- Materials and trainings for data depositors (how to prepare data for inclusion in the archive, how to deposit prepared data)
 - Materials and trainings for data users (how to find data in the catalogue, how to download data)
 - Support, assistance, and advice for data depositors and data users
 - Promotional activities and outreach to users
 - Regional collaboration and establishment of networks of service users
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OPTIONAL SERVICES AND ACTIVITIES

- Creation and maintenance of a research inventory of existing research projects (with or without data)
 - Online tools for data analysis and variable exploration - creating tables, graphs and other analytical results
 - Data management training for researchers
 - Purchased access to foreign databases (e.g., ICPSR, LIS) for national researchers
 - Wider promotion of “open access” to data
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AFTER THE END OF THE PROJECT

Danger zone: Staff!

- Continuing to offer services as a part of a regular job?
 - Is this possible? How much time can be allocated?
 - Identify services which can be offered without any external support
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PROBLEM WITH SENSITIVE DATA

- What if somebody wants to deposit sensitive data?
 - What if somebody asks about using restricted data (communication with the data owner is needed)?
 - Who will sign the depositor and user contracts?
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TODAY'S CHALLENGE

Imagine a scenario without funding.

Clearly define and communicate selected services to (potential) users in a honest way.

SUGGESTIONS FROM THE AUDIENCE ?

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION

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